

FURQAT IJODIDA AN‘ANAVIYLIK VA O‘ZIGA XOSLIK

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Furqat ijodining sharq mumtoz she‘riyati bilan hamohangligi, ustozlar an‘analarining shoir ijodiga ta‘siri, shuningdek, uning she‘riyatiga xos bo‘lgan o‘ziga xos jihatlar haqida so‘z boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: An‘ana va izdoshlik, g‘azal, muxammas, tatabbu, taxmis, yor, oshiq, ishq, hijron, hasbi hol.

TRADITIONALITY AND UNIQUENESS IN FURQAT'S CREATION

Abstract. This article talks about the harmony of Furqat's work with eastern classisal sharia, the influence of the traditions of the teachers on the poet's work, and the specific aspects of his poetry.

Keywords: Tradition and followership, ghazal, muxammas, tatabbu, guess, mistress, in love, love, hijran, case in point.

ТРАДИЦИОННОСТЬ И УНИКАЛЬНОСТЬ В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ ФУРКАТА

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о созвучии творчества Фурката с восточной классической поэзией, влиянии традиций его учителей на творчество поэта, а также о специфических аспектах его поэзии.

Ключевые слова: Традиция и преемственность, газель, мухаммаса, татаббу, тахмис, влюбленные, любовь, хиджран, хасби хол.

Mumtoz she‘riyat mana necha asrlardan beri rivojlanib, sayqal topib kelmoqda. SHarq mumtoz she‘riyati o‘ziga xos an‘analarga asoslangani bilan ham e‘tiborlidir. Kimki shoirlikka da‘vo qilar ekan, o‘zidan oldin o‘tgan ijodkorlar ijodini qunt bilan o‘rganishi va ustozlariga hurmat saqlagan holda bu go‘zal an‘analarni davom ettirishi hamda salaflari ijodidan o‘ttiz ming, zamondosh shoirlari ijodidan esa yigirma ming bayt she‘r yod bilishi lozim bo‘lgan. An‘ana ijodkor uchun mayoq vazifasini bajaradi. Iste‘dod egalari shu an‘analar asosida o‘z uslublari va yo‘nalishlarini topadilar.

Furqat o‘z asarlarida o‘zidan oldin o‘tgan salaflarining ishlarini davom ettirish bilan birga adabiyotimizda o‘z so‘zi va uslubini yarata oldi. Shoir uchun eng kerakli narsalardan biri mutolaa ekanligini yaxshi anglagan Furqat navbati bilan sharq buyuk ijodkorlari asarlarini mutolaa qilib o‘rganib bordi. Jumladan, sakkiz yoshida olti oy mobaynida Farididdin Attorning „Mantiq ut-tayr“ dostoni mutolaasiga band bo‘ladi. Keyin Xo‘ja Hofiz devoni mutolaasiga o‘tadi. So‘ng besh oy davomida Mirzo Bedil g‘azaliyoti bahriga sho‘ng‘iydi. To‘qqiz yoshida esa Alisher Navoiyning „Chor devon‘ini o‘qishga kirishadi.¹

Furqat lirikasida ham mumtoz adabiyotimizning boshqa vakillarida bo‘lgani singari g‘azal janri yetakchilik qiladi. Furqat g‘azallarida biz Navoiy, Amiriy, Fuzuliy, Bedil kabi ijodkorlarning bevosita ta‘sirini kuzatishimiz mumkin. Shu bilan birga Furqat she‘rlarida o‘ziga xos ohang va

¹ Ochilov E. Furqat ijodida Navoiy an‘analari.// O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti. 6. 2019. – T.:Fan. – B.13

hech kimda uchramaydigan go‘zal tashbehlarni uchratamiz. Bu esa, albatta, Furqat asarlari badiiy qimmatini yanada oshiradi.

Furqat ijodiga, ayniqsa, sharqning buyuk shoiri Navoiyning ta‘siri katta. Darhaqiqat, Furqat ko‘ngliga she‘r havasi tushgan bolaligidan to she‘riyat maydonida javlon urgan umrining nihoyasigacha bu buyuk salafi ta‘sirida qalam tebratdi. Ustoz so‘z san‘tkorining ko‘plab g‘azallariga tatabbu bog‘ladi, turli fikr-u tashbehlarni yangicha sharoitda rivojlantirdi va ularning yangi qirralarini ochib yanada rivojlantirdi. Navoiy ta‘sirini uning har bir asarida sezishimiz mumkin. ² Furqat Navoiyning “Aylab”, “Aylagach”, “Aylay desam bor”, “Isi”, “Kelmadi” radifli qator g‘azallariga tatabbular qilgan. Masalan, g‘azal mulkning sultonining

Gar bahor el topsa bo‘stondin rayhon isi,

Kelur ul rayhon ila guldin manga hijron isi.

matla‘li g‘azaliga

Elga keldi to bahor ayyomi gar bo‘ston isi,

Yor ko‘yidin kelar menga gul-u rizvon isi

Bilan boshlanadigan tatabbu yozadi. Har ikki g‘azal ham yetti baytdan. G‘azal ham tatabbu ham ramali musammani maqsurda (foilotun, foilotun, foilotun, foilun) vaznida.

Furqat tatabbulari hamisha ham Navoiy g‘azallariga hamqofiya va hamradif emas- u ba‘zida boshqa qofiya va radifda ham tatabbular yaratadi. Masalan, “Koshki” radifli g‘azaliga boshqa qofiyada tatabbu qilsa, “Kelmadi” radifli g‘azaliga “kelur” radifli tatabbu qiladi. Chunonchi, uning:

Har kishikim, dahr aro sendek malaksiy mosi bor,

Xuri Jannat yuziga boqmoqdin istig‘nosi bor,-

bayti bilan boshlanadigan g‘azali buyuk salafining

Kimki oning bir malaksiymo parivash yori bor,

Odamiy bo‘lsa, pari birla malakdin ori bor-

matla‘li g‘azaliga ergashib yaratilgani shubhasiz. Ko‘rinib turibdiki, bunda radif saqlangan bo‘lsa ham qofiya tizimi yangilangan.

Furqat Navoiyning “Yor bo‘lmoq tong emas men zor-u rasvo birla do‘st”, “Tun oqshom keldi kulbam sori ul gulrux shitob aylab”, “Sahvdur tubi demak ra‘no niholingni ko‘rib “misralari bilan boshlanadigan g‘azallariga g‘o‘zal taxmislar bog‘lagan. ³

Shoir g‘azallarida, shuningdek, mumtoz adabiyotimizning boshqa buyuk namoyondalarining ham ta‘siri seziladi. Xususan, Atoiyning

Jamoling vasfini qildim chamanda,

Qizordi gul uyottin anjumanda-

matla‘li mashhur g‘azali barchamizga ma‘lum. Furqatning

Yuz-u qadding ko‘rib, jono, chamanda,

Asiring bo‘ldi gul, shamshod banda-

matla‘si bilan boshlanuvchi g‘azali Atoiy g‘azali ta‘sirida yaratilgani ko‘rinib turibdi.

Atoiy g‘azalida oshiq bog‘ sahnida ma‘shuqaning vasfini kuylagan zamon uning ta‘rifini eshitgan gul o‘zining bu maqomda emasligidan uyalib qizarib ketadi. Furqat g‘azalida endi gul

² O‘sha manba – B.13

³ Ochilov E. Furqat ijodida Navoiy an‘analari.// O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti. 6. 2019. – T.:Fan. – B.15

obrazi oldiga shamshod daraxti ham qo‘shiladi. Ular yorning nafaqat tarifini eshitishadi balki uning go‘zalligini o‘z ko‘zlari bilan ko‘rib asiru banda bo‘lishadi. Ko‘rinib turibdiki, ikkala tasvir ham bir birga yaqin va ayni paytda o‘ziga xos hamdir.

Furqat o‘z g‘azalida tug‘ilgan o‘lkasi – Qo‘qon nomini ham keltirib o‘tadi.

Nigorim, ko‘r madim sendek parivash,

Xudo haqqi qalamviri Xo‘qanda

G‘azal maqta’sida Furqat hasb – u hol tarzida o‘zining vatandan olisda ekanligini takidlab o‘tadi.

Quyundek, Furqatiy, kezdin jahonni,

Ajab sargashta men dashti Xo‘tanda.

Furqat yana bir buyuk ijodkor, shoh va shoir Amir Umarxon (taxallusi Amiriy) ijodini sevib mutolaa qilgan. Furqat ijodiga Amiriy g‘azallarining ta’siri xususida adabiyotshunos Zebo Qobilova o‘zining “Furqatning Amiriy g‘azallariga tatabbulari” nomli maqolasida qimmatli fikrlarni keltirib o‘tadi

Furqat yashab ijod etgan davrda Qo‘qonda Amiriy shaxsiyati va she‘riyati ham mashhur edi. Muqimiy, Zavqiy, Muhyi, Rojiy, Nisbat kabi shoir do‘stlari qatorida Furqat ham uning merosidan bahramand bo‘lib dilo‘rtar g‘azallaridan ilhomlanib, betakror tashbehlaridan ta’sirlanib qator she‘rlar yaratgan. O‘zini to‘lqinlantirgan she‘rlariga tatabbular qilgan.⁴

Aytaylik, Amiriyning zamondosh ijodkorlar va o‘zidan keyingi Qalam ahliga kuchli ta’sir ko‘rsatgan va ko‘plab tatabbularning vujudga kelishiga sabab bo‘lgan “Lab uyur takallunga, zulfni parishon qil” misrasi bilan boshlanadigan mashhur g‘azali bor. Unda jumladan shunday bayt mavjud:

Ehtisob uchun zohid kirsda dayr aro, soqiy

Bir qadah bilan aning zuhdidin pushaymon qil.

Endi mazkur baytni Furqatning quyidagi bayti bilan qiyoslang

Loladek jamolingni bir yo‘la ko‘rib zohid,

Necha yilki zuhdidin dog‘ o‘lub pushaymondur.

Furqatning bu baytida Amiriyning bevosita bo‘lmasa-da bilvosita ta’sirini sezamiz.

Amiriy o‘z taxallusini ko‘plab she‘rlarida ikki ma‘noda qo‘llaydi. Ham taxallus, ham sulton, shoh, amir. Furqat ham Amiriy kabi ismini ko‘p o‘rinlarda ikki ma‘noda qo‘llaydi: taxallus va ayriliq. Shoir nomi yoki taxallusining ham taxallus ham lug‘aviy ma‘nosida qo‘llanilishidan iborat bunday san‘at ilmi bade‘da ittifoq deb ataladi. Masalan, Amiriy:

Kimki qildi yor ko‘yida gadolig‘ ixtiyor,

Saltanat iqlimida derlar Amiri kamyob.

Furqat:

Maqomim bo‘ldi sahro-lola yang‘lig‘,

Yurakda dog‘i Furqat lahza-lahza.⁵

Mumtoz adabiyotimizda yorni mukammal hilqat sifatida tariflash, uning qoshlarini kamon, ko‘zlarini ohu, sochlarini sumbul, qomatini shamshod deya vasf qilish an-ana tusiga kirgan. Furqat ham bu an‘anaga sodiq qolgan holda, ma’shuqani jamiki go‘zallaiklar sultoni tarzida

⁴ Qobilova Z. Furqatning Amiriy g‘azallariga tatabbulari. // O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti. 6.2019. – T.: Fan. – B.21

⁵ Qobilova Z. Furqatning Amiriy g‘azallariga tatabbulari. // O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti. 6.2019. – T.: Fan. – B.21

tasvirlaydi. Shu bilan bir qatorda ifodaga yangicha yoʻnalish va ohang qoʻshadi. Shoirning Fuzuliy gʻazaliga tazmin tariqasida yozilgan “Surmadin koʻzlar qaro” sheʼrida mashuqa shunday tasvirlanadiki, oʻquvchi koʻz oʻngida ikki yuzi qizarib, ibo bilan kulimsirab turgan kelinchak obrazi jonli gavdalanadi.

Surmadin koʻzlar qaro, qoʻllar xinodin lolarang,
Gʻoʻzadin yuzlarda tob-u, oʻsmadin qoshlar tarang.
Zafaroniy koʻylak uzra argʻuvoniy kamzuhur,
Roʻymol ogʻushidin peshonani ahvoli tang.
Bori nozik panjalar oltin uzukdin zebnok,
Qoʻl bilarzukdin muzayyan, nuqradin ogʻizda chang.⁶

Ushbu toʻrt bayt davomida shoir goʻzalning tashqi koʻrinish portretini yaratgan boʻlsa, quyidagi misralarda endi xatti-harakatlarini tasvirlash orqali uning xarakter xususiyatlarini ochib beradi.

Gʻamza birla oʻlturur, ham jilvalar birla yurur,
Turfa bir noz, ofarin, pur ishva tannaz-u satang.
Aql hush eltar agar tursa paridek silkinib,
Odamizod ichra ham bundoq boʻlurmu shoʻx-shang.

Furqat ijodini oʻrganar ekanmiz, undagi baʼzi ohanglar Bobur sheʼriyatini ham esga solishini koʻrishimiz mumkin. Ikkalasida vatandan olisdalik va gʻurbat hissi yetakchilik qiladi. Bu ikki ijodkor ham umrining koʻp qismini ona yurtidan olisda, yurt sogʻinchi bilan oʻtkazishdi. Bu sogʻinch hissi esa ikkala ijodkorning ham asarlarida oʻz aksini koʻrsatmay qolmadi, albatta. Shuningdek, Furqat va Bobur ijodi oʻrtasidagi yana bir mushtarak jihat til jihatdan sodda, tushunarli va xalqonalikdir. Oddiy misralar bilan yuksak sanʼat namunasi yaratib, oʻquvchi his-tuygʻulariga taʼsir qila olish qobiliyati ikki ijodkorga ham xosdir. Xususan, Boburning nasriy uslubda yozilgan “Boburnoma” asari biografik asar boʻlib unda ijodkor oʻzi guvohi boʻlgan va boshidan oʻtkazgan voqealarni sodda, tushunarli va badiiy tarzda hikoya qilib beradi. Furqat ham shunday nasriy tarjimai hol yaratgan va uni “Hoʻqandlik shoir Zokirjon Furqatning ahvoloti. Oʻzi yozgʻoni” deb ataydi. Shoir dunyoqarashi va ijtimoiy-ijodiy faoliyatini belgilashda favqulotda ahamiyatga ega boʻlgan bu asar, oʻsha davrda endigina shakllanayotgan oʻzbek publitsistikasining yorqin namunasi sifatida ham ahamiyatga ega.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Furqat oʻz ijodi davomida ustozlari anʼanalarini munosib tarzda davom ettirdi, adabiyotimiz xazinasini durdona asarlar bilan boyitdi va oʻzidan keying avlod uchun munosib ijod maktabi qoldirdi.

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⁶ Furqat. Tanlangan asarlar. – T.: Gʻafur Gʻulom nomidagi adabiyot va sanʼat nashriyoti, 1975. – B.47

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